

Punjab/Delhi, India

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Entry tags: Sikh traditions, Hinduism, Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Indic Religious Traditions

Punjab region, India.

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Modern Punjab through Delhi Corridor

Region tags: South Asia, India, Rajasthan, Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh

28.5-32 degrees North, 74-77.5 degrees East.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Islam-Rather large, yet minority; Hinduism and Sikhism-large although neither an absolute majority. Participation for all three religions includes wide range of population, especially as devotional movements incorporate many potentially excluded or marginalized by more elite practice.

Beliefs

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Islam-supernatural beings include both Monotheistic God as well as revered Sufi practitioners, often at burial site.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Wide variety of deities and supernatural figures.

– Yes

Notes: Sikhism-supernatural beings include both a Monotheistic God as well as revered devotees.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Islam-Ramadan fasting.

– I don't know

Notes: Sikhism-Unsure, likely not.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-Yes, both elite and familial practice.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Islam-prohibitions on alcohol, non-halal food.

– Yes

Notes: Sikhism-prohibitions on tobacco.

– Yes

Notes: Hinduism-part of fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Yes for Islam, Sikhism, and Hinduism.

Society and Institutions

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Islam-Tradition of supporting poor, feeding of needy.

– Yes

Notes: Sikhism-Langur involves feeding of public as part of religious works.

– Yes

Notes: • Hinduism-Yes, although providing of alms to poor arguably less institutionalized than either Sikhism or Islam.